

ISic1135

I.Sicily inscription 1135

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 159

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀριστόδαμος Νεμηνίδα Πέρσιος ποιητὰς
2. τοὺς γονέας καὶ τὸν εὐεργέταν αὐτῶντα
3. Ἀριστόδαμον Σμῖα καὶ τὰν γυναῖκα αὐτοῦ
4. καὶ τὰν ἰδίαν ἀνέστασε

Apparatus

Text of IGTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285051

EDR 135921

EDCS 64900787

PHI 140620

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1135. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351601>